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Adaptive Façades in Practice: Investigating Predesign Challenges and Opportunities for Sustainable Architecture

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Abstract: Adaptive façade systems have emerged as an advanced technology, offering thermal control and modulating daylighting while lowering energy consumption, all of which contribute to supporting the liveability of dense urban communities. These systems provide significant financial and ecological benefits, which render them a prudent future investment towards developing sustainable cities and communities. Nevertheless, it requires larger initial investments, which could hinder their adoption in facade designs. This study aims to investigate practitioners' perspectives on adaptive façades' potential in advancing sustainable, energy-efficient architecture, with particular emphasis on addressing the challenges they face during the predesign phase of adoption. An online survey was administered to collect professional opinions from architects, engineers, and other professionals from several regions. Despite professionals' respect for the lasting advantages of energy efficiency and occupants' comfort, key findings identify several challenges to implementing adaptive façades, including a lack of awareness among customers, high initial expenditures, and a shortage of experienced specialists. The initial cost of the systems and maintenance was highlighted by the respondents as a key challenge. The study offers a set of recommendations to overcome the identified challenges, including the value of raising awareness through workshops, training, and real-world case studies that support the creation of a sustainable built environment.

Keywords: Adaptive façade; Architecture practice; Pre-design stage; Sustainable architecture

Main highlights:

Lack of customers' awareness and specialists' experience are key challenges of adaptive facade adoption.

The practitioners consider the initial cost of adaptive systems as a key challenge

Educational programmes integrating adapted façades are seen by practitioners as helping increase awareness

Practitioners generally hold moderate to strong optimism about adaptable façades in relation to saving energy.

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Introduction

Designing sustainable, affordable, and high-performance buildings has become critical for tackling both environmental and human needs. The way the built environment is designed must change to serve environmental goals while also improving occupants' well-being (Ghaffarianhoseini, 2016). Among other design technologies, adaptive façades have emerged over the past decades as an innovation in this progression, offering dynamic building envelope systems that adjust in real time to environmental elements, including light, temperature, humidity, and wind. Unlike static façades, these systems use receptors, smart materials, and/or control mechanisms to manage solar gain, ventilation, and daylighting, thereby adapting to outdoor conditions and enhancing indoor comfort levels. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2020), energy-responsive designs can reduce energy consumption by up to 50% compared to traditional static structures. This promises a practical solution for creating sustainable buildings that are adaptive to climate change and sensitive to human needs. From a cost point of view, while the initial costs may be substantial, long-term savings and increased performance frequently justify the investment (Chwieduk, 2003).

In this research, we place particular emphasis on addressing the challenges that arise during the early design stages through analyzing expert interviews to identify key adoption barriers of adaptive facades' systems, including technological, financial, and practicality hurdles. These aspects have wider implications on the adoption of such technology; therefore, a review of the literature was conducted to highlight some of the most important aspects that need to be considered in the decision-making stage.

Literature Review

As buildings account for about 40% of global energy use (IEA, 2020), façades play a crucial role in reducing heating, cooling, and lighting demands (Loonen, 2017). Adaptive façades, in particular, were developed to dynamically respond to environmental conditions, enhancing energy efficiency, modulate daylight, control glare, and offer view to the outside. Fundamentally, building facades can be categorised into passive, dynamic and responsive façades. Passive façade systems rely on the inherent properties of materials and design strategies to regulate outdoor conditions. This can be seen in the example of *Manitoba Hydro Place, Canada* was designed with double-skin façades and natural ventilation strategies to cut energy use by up to 60% and enhance occupant comfort (Gratia and Herde, 2007). Dynamic façades, on the other hand, incorporate moving elements that physically change position or shape automatically or manually by users. An example can be seen in the *Bloomberg HQ in London* which uses movable bronze fins and a smart ventilation system to optimize solar gain and air quality, reducing energy use by 35% (Foster + Partners, 2017). Responsive façades adjust their mechanism or material properties in reaction to environmental changes, e.g., light, heat, humidity, etc (Heidari Matin, 2022). Recently, advancements in smart materials and integration techniques have made adaptive façades more viable in order to achieve environmental responsiveness. These systems help maintain stable indoor temperatures, reduce temperature fluctuations, improve energy efficiency, ensure optimal light conditions and minimise glare. According to Loonen (2017), a responsive facade can reduce electricity consumption by 20-40%, depending on climate and building use. Germany's *SurPLUShome*, is an example that demonstrates the successful integration of adaptive façade technology that results in generating twice the electricity it consumes, showcasing exceptional energy

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efficiency. The project features mechanical louvres that enhance thermal comfort by regulating indoor temperatures, and minimizing energy use for heating and cooling. This climate-responsive system resulted in cutting energy consumption by 30% while improving occupant comfort (Loonen, 2013).

From the users' health front, adaptive façades significantly enhance human comfort by addressing key factors such as thermal and visual comfort, leading to improvement in the overall users' satisfaction and well-being outcomes (Tzempelikos & Shen, 2013; Aksamija, 2013). Additionally, adaptive façades can act as acoustic barriers, reducing noise levels and improving acoustic comfort in urban environments. Because of diverging preferences found in multi-cultural urban regions, adaptive façades offer a multiple proposition by not only responding to climatic conditions but also reinforcing cultural identity and meeting human psychological and physiological needs (Veitch & Newsham, 2000; IEA, 2021). Al Bahar Towers is an example of a culturally inspired designs, which fuse advanced responsive shading systems with Islamic architectural motifs that dynamically respond to the sun exposure (Attia, 2012).

Although these systems require higher initial investments, research shows that they offer significant long-term cost-effectiveness through reduced energy consumption and lower maintenance demands (Guggemos & Horvath, 2005; Aksamija, 2013). For instance, Young Hee's study of a nine-story office building in a cold climate revealed a 23% reduction in overall energy use and over 20% savings in cooling needs during summer (Bonham & Kim, 2022). Beyond operational savings, these systems enhance property value, appeal to sustainability-focused investors, and help meet increasingly strict energy efficiency regulations (Hwang & Tan, 2012; Wymelenberg, 2014).

While adaptive systems offer long-term energy and comfort benefits, the complexity of their dynamics and responsiveness to environmental conditions can pose significant challenges in design, upfront cost, calibration, maintenance and regulatory consideration (IEA, 2021), making designers reluctant to adopt them in early-stage design. Moreover, inadequate calibration strategies or overlooked maintenance considerations at this phase can compromise system utilization during the decision-making stage. This highlights the necessity of integrating thoughtful design decisions early on, with a focus on long-term operability, maintainability, and system resilience (Hensen and Loonen, 2017). In this context, it is speculated that stakeholder education and early design-stage planning can bridge this gap, as acknowledged in the scientific literature (Loonen et al., 2017; Aksamija, 2013).

In this research, we aim to explore practitioners' perspectives on the transformative potential of adaptive façades in advancing sustainable, energy-efficient architecture, with particular emphasis on addressing the challenges they face during the predesign phase of adoption. The outcome intends to provide developers and policymakers with actionable insights to support the broad incorporation of adaptive façades into sustainable construction practices.

Methodology

This study adopted an online survey approach to fulfil the research aim. Survey methods have been widely used in architectural design research, facilitated the collection of responses from professionals in multiple geographical locations. The survey was distributed during January

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2025 using Google Forms to architects, engineers, designers, and sustainability consultants from several worldwide areas.

The survey design was informed by the literature review, which looked at peer-reviewed journals, industry reports, and technical publications to learn about adaptable façade technologies, their energy performance, aesthetic and functional features, and adoption challenges such as cost, system complexity, and regulation limits. The study's design ensured credibility through methodological triangulation, which combined academic and practical inputs to answer the research question: How do early design decisions by architects and clients influence the adoption of adaptive façades, and what barriers and opportunities exist for aligning expectations? This method not only addressed existing gaps in the literature but also produced practical insights that would help to promote the incorporation of adaptive façade systems in future sustainable buildings. The poll included both closed-ended questions about metrics like cost-effectiveness, energy savings, and architectural appeal, as well as open-ended questions that allowed participants to express their personal experiences and professional issues with adaptive façades. The combination of qualitative and quantitative data allowed for a more comprehensive knowledge of stakeholder attitudes, practical design barriers, and prospective integration methods. To effectively demonstrate trends, viewpoints, and major discoveries, data were analysed using descriptive statistics. The research was conducted considering ethical standards. Participants gave informed consent and were assured of anonymity and the voluntary nature of their participation. Data was anonymised and securely kept, with only authorised persons having access to it. The sampling method and the survey were approved by the ethical committee at De Montfort University, UK.

Results and Discussion

Overview

The analysis of the survey captured a diverse and insightful range of responses from 31 industry professionals, including designers (48.4%), principal architects (25.8%), engineers (22.6%) and other consultants (3.2%). Geographically, the majority of responses came from Nigeria (48.4%), followed by India (19.4%), the United Kingdom (15.1%), and Germany (6.5%). The rest of the responses were received equally from Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Australia. While this sample highlights a strong design-oriented viewpoint, it also reflects a variety of cultural and environmental contexts. The majority of participants had under 10 years of experience, showcasing perspectives from early- to mid-career professionals. Most of the participants work on residential buildings (64.5%), followed by mixed-use buildings (19.4%) and commercial buildings (9.7%). The remaining participants work on other types of buildings. Notably, familiarity with adaptive façade technologies ranged between moderate and advanced for most of the respondents, with 25.8% rating their knowledge at level 6 on a scale of 1–10, and only 3.2% placing themselves at the highest levels of expertise. This level of experience and geographically skewed sample reflects increasing design goals that encourage innovation and adaptation of use. The investigation conducted a thorough analysis of survey data on the adoption and integration of adaptive façades in sustainable building design, with an emphasis on human comfort, energy efficiency, cost, and predesign factors.

Practitioners' views on responsive façade

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The survey results reveal clear preferences regarding the perceived importance of key factors in adaptive façade design. In essence, human comfort emerged as the highest priority, with the majority of respondents ranking it as the most important consideration. Energy efficiency and cost-effectiveness were both viewed as moderately important, receiving a balanced distribution of rankings, particularly across positions one to three. In contrast, aesthetic appeal was consistently rated as the least important, with a significant proportion of participants assigning it the lowest rank (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Respondants' views on the importance of adaptive façades

The overwhelming majority of respondents acknowledged their involvement in design processes that consider improving natural light (35.5%), utilizing dynamic shading elements to reduce heat transfer (32.3%) and encourage natural ventilation (22.6%), hence lowering dependability on mechanical systems. A smaller percentage of respondents utilized smart glazing technologies, thermal insulation or photovoltaic panels.

Due to aesthetic considerations, the adaptation of responsive façades was largely praised, with 71% ranked them as highly appealing (4 or 5 stars), see Figure 2. This enthusiastic endorsement emphasizes the designs' visual appeal and the universal appreciation for their original appearance. A lesser proportion (25.8%) ranked their aesthetic appeal as moderate (3 stars), implying that while the designs are satisfactory, they may not stand out to everyone. Negative feedback was minimal, with only one response giving the lowest rating (1 star) and no two-star evaluations. This general acceptance reinforces the notion that adapted façades are greatly identified for their aesthetic characteristics, which can be a powerful driver for adoption.

In terms of functionality, the feedback was generally positive. As such, the majority of respondents saw the practical benefits of adapted façades, with 38.7% of responses rated them as high (4 stars) while 25.8% gave them the highest rating (5 stars). This displays a strong belief in the design's utilitarian worth. While 29% provided an achievable rating (3 stars), just 6.5% evaluated functionality as low (2 stars), and no respondents assessed it as very low (1 star). This indicates that skepticisms regarding the technology's functional benefits is low, and that plenty of individuals see it as a practical and useful solution. Assessments of cost-efficiency were more balanced, showing a combination of optimism and caution. The majority of participants (32.3%) ranked cost-efficiency at three stars, suggesting a neutral approach, while 32.3% awarded it four stars and 12.9% gave it five stars. Together, these findings indicate that many

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individuals regard cost-efficiency as favourable but may require additional evidence of long-term savings to be totally convinced. On the other hand, pessimism prevails, with 6.5% and 16.1% evaluating cost-efficiency as one or two stars. These concerns underline the importance for architects and designers to give clear examples, case studies, and cost-benefit analysis evaluations to show that adaptive façades are financially viable.

Above are images of different adaptive façade designs. Please rate each based on its: Attractiveness (1 is low rating -5 high rating stars)
31 responses

Perceived functionality
31 responses

Estimated cost-efficiency
31 responses

Figure 2 Respondents' views on aesthetic, functionality and cost-efficiency aspects of responsive facades

Challenges to implementing responsive facade

Figure 3 identifies several challenges to implementing adaptive façades reported by the respondents, including a lack of awareness (45.2%), high initial expenditures (32.3%), a shortage of experienced specialists (9.7%), uncertainty regarding long-term performance (9.7%), and mild reluctance to new technology (3.2%). Spotting the lack of awareness by the majority of the practitioners essentially suggests that stakeholders to prioritise raising awareness through education and marketing, delivering financial incentives, investing in

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professional training, and sharing long-term performance data. These solutions will help to overcome constraints and promote wider usage of adapted façades.

What do you think is the main reason adaptive façade technology is not widely adopted?

31 responses

Figure 3 Respondents' views on potential challenges to implementing adaptive façades

The results also suggest an almost even split in opinions on whether the cost of adapted façades outweighs the advantages (see Figure 4). As such, 51.6% of respondents say the cost is prohibitively high, citing worries about early investment and maintenance, while 48.4% see value in long-term benefits, including reduced energy usage and sustainability. This split implies a variety of priorities, suggesting that decision-makers in the building and architectural industries need to emphasize the long-term worth of adaptive façades in order to counter doubts. More research and case studies on their cost-effectiveness could help move public attitudes towards greater acceptability.

On the other hand, to gain deeper insight into respondents' perspectives on the barriers to adopting responsive façades, particularly concerns related to cost, we included a question aimed at evaluating whether participants believe the financial investment required for adaptive façade systems outweighs their perceived benefits. According to the survey results in Figure 5, 61.3% of respondents recognized the benefits of adapted façades but are held back by cost concerns. A smaller population (16.1%) is willing to pay more at first in exchange for future rewards, whereas 12.9% prefer to pay as little as possible up front. A small portion (9.7%) is still in doubt, emphasizing the need for more information dissemination. This suggests that, to remedy this, stakeholders could provide cash rewards and display successful projects that demonstrate long-term savings.

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Do you believe the cost of implementing adaptive façades outweighs the benefits? Why or why not?

31 responses

Figure 4 Respondents' views on adaptive façade cost versus benefits

Do you think users or clients are ready to include adaptive façade technology in their designs despite its higher costs?

31 responses

Figure 5 Respondents' views on clients' readiness to implement adaptive facades in their projects

Energy efficiency consideration

The results in Figure 6 indicate that 54.8% of respondents expect adaptable façades to save them between 10% and 30% of their energy, indicating moderate optimism and realistic expectations. Meanwhile, 45.2% anticipate savings might be 30-50% or more, suggesting strong faith in the technology. Notably, no respondents anticipate less than 10% savings or express hesitation, indicating widespread trust in the technology's good influence on energy efficiency. These findings highlight the need of which include adaptive façades in building designs and aligning services with market expectations in order to boost uptake and confidence among construction and designing stakeholders.

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How much energy savings do you believe adaptive façades can provide?

31 responses

Figure 6 Respondents' expectations on energy savings from adaptive façade utilisation

Conclusion

This paper explores practitioners' perspectives on the expectations and potential of adaptive façades in advancing sustainable, energy-efficient architecture. An online survey was used to provide an understanding of professional perspectives on adaptive façades in building design. With responses from 31 industry professionals, primarily designers and architects, the findings reflect a design-oriented viewpoint shaped by diverse environmental and cultural contexts. Most participants were early- to mid-career professionals working mainly on residential and mixed-use projects. Adaptive façades were widely appreciated for their aesthetic and functional qualities. A majority (71%) rated their visual appeal highly, and 64.5% acknowledged their energy-saving potential, highlighting these aspects as key motivators for adoption. However, cost remains a critical barrier. Opinions were split on whether long-term benefits justify the initial expense, with 61.3% citing financial concerns despite recognizing the advantages. This underscores the need for more accessible case studies, financial analysis, and evidence-based demonstrations of long-term value. Functionality received generally positive ratings, though moderate scores indicate some reservations, particularly about newer technologies like smart glazing and photovoltaics, which were less commonly used. Barriers such as lack of awareness (45.2%), high initial costs (32.3%), and a shortage of experienced professionals (9.7%) were identified as key challenges to implementation. Encouragingly, there is strong optimism about energy performance, with 54.8% expecting 10–30% savings and 45.2% anticipating savings up to 50% or more. These expectations signal strong confidence in the technology's potential if financial and educational hurdles can be overcome. To support wider adoption, stakeholders should focus on raising awareness, offering financial incentives, investing in professional training, and showcasing successful applications. By addressing concerns around cost and long-term performance, adaptive façades can become a more accessible and mainstream solution in climate-responsive design.

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